

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11148484>

ABSTRACT

Interactive methods are teaching methods that can encourage active participation and collaboration among students. They are particularly effective in foreign language teaching because they allow students to practice speaking, listening, reading, and writing in a natural and communicative way. This article highlights the modern methods of organizing the educational process in English language teaching, taking into account the efforts and opportunities aimed at the education sector, especially foreign language teaching in our republic.

Keywords: interactive methods, language teaching, foreign languages, learning environment, educational process, communication skills

As is known, great attention began to be paid to the education sector after our country gained independence. In particular, the need and demand for teaching foreign languages (English) has increased. Therefore, increasing the efficiency of the lesson in teaching foreign languages is one of the most urgent and important tasks. In addition, the Resolution "On additional measures to improve the study of foreign languages", adopted on January 20, 2022, [<https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5831978>] contains a number of proposals, such as "developing and implementing information and communication technologies, software projects to promote the study of foreign languages; creating videos, games, entertainment shows, films, and other educational content for a thorough mastery of foreign languages, the formation of basic language skills; attracting highly qualified specialists, including local and foreign experts, based on civil law contracts." These proposals in the resolution ensure that the process of learning foreign languages becomes even more interesting and high-quality. Therefore, it is advisable to use innovative technologies in teaching English in the educational process. For this process, teachers can use videos related to the topic and videos of various dialogues and conversations during the lesson. These make a great contribution to the formation of the skills of watching, listening, and understanding at the same time in students.

There are many methods and directions for organizing the educational process to increase students' activity, interest in the lesson, and critical thinking skills. Interactive methods based on the activity of students in the lesson are the most effective method of these directions. The concept of "interactive" is expressed in English as "interact", and its lexical meaning is "inter" - mutual, and "act" means action. It should be noted that traditional education is organized based on conversation (dialogue), and the participants of this conversation can be teacher-student, student-student, or groups. As you can see, interactive methods are implemented directly through the activity of students and the teacher; based on students' conversations, communications, and heated discussions. Such joint activities and processes play an important

role in improving students' communication and speech skills, expanding their knowledge and skills, and developing their free-thinking skills. Furthermore, these interactive methods can help students to:

- find a solution to problem situations together, in a team;
- create intimacy in the learning process;
- develop the ability to express personal decisions without hesitation;
- increase responsibility for the educational process

There are many methods that serve to increase interactivity in students, and we will introduce them below:

- "Buzz" exercise. In this method, participants unite in a group focused on one topic. Each student from each group expresses his/her opinion on the topic and makes his/her contribution to the group. Each student in each group is encouraged by the teacher. As a teacher, you can give your students keywords to start the conversation.
- "Problem solving" (Creative problem solving) for this method, the teacher reads a story and the students brainstorm and continue the story, i.e. the ending of the story is referred to the student's judgment.
- The "When pictures speak" method helps to improve the speech abilities of students. In this case, the students are presented with pictures related to the topic and they work based on the pictures.
- In the "Quiz cards" method, cards with questions related to the topic are distributed to students according to their number and they answer the questions on these cards.

Interactive methods can be used in a variety of foreign language teaching contexts, including classrooms, online learning environments, and language immersion programs. By using interactive methods, teachers can create a more engaging and effective learning experience for their students. These teaching methods can bring about the following benefits:

- **Increased student engagement:** Interactive methods help to keep students engaged and motivated by providing them with opportunities to actively participate in the learning process.
- **Improved communication skills:** Interactive methods allow students to practice speaking and listening to the target language in a variety of contexts. This helps them to develop fluency and accuracy.
- **Enhanced vocabulary and grammar:** Interactive methods provide students with opportunities to use new vocabulary and grammar in a meaningful way. This helps them to retain information and improve their overall language skills.
- **Greater cultural awareness:** Interactive methods often incorporate cultural elements into the learning process. This helps students to develop an understanding and appreciation of the target culture.
- **Improved critical thinking skills:** Interactive methods encourage students to think critically about the language and to use their own creativity to solve problems.

Accordingly, each interactive method has its own specific goals and objectives and each of them helps to increase the student's potential. As the modern education system of our time demands young people who are leaders in any field and experts in their field, we, future teachers, can make our contribution to the future of our country by effectively using innovative technologies and taking advantage of the opportunities created by our President.

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